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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 2

Pages: 156-172

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2656

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14208264

Manuscript Accepted: 11-06-2024

Challenges and Coping Mechanisms Toward the Pre-board Performance of LET Takers

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the challenges and coping mechanisms that affect the pre-board performance of the LET takers. The study employed simple random sampling. The total number of respondents who participated in the study were 130 LET takers at Catalyst Pro Tutorial and Review Center in Iligan. A descriptive-correlational design was used. Descriptive research used in describing socio-economic profile and the challenges and coping mechanisms of LET takers. It is also correlational research since the socio-economic profile, the challenges and, the coping mechanisms of let takers were correlated to the pre-board performance of the LET takers. Hence, these findings underscore the multifaceted nature of challenges faced by students during examination preparation, encompassing personal, financial, and familial domains. these findings underscore the importance of employing a diverse range of coping mechanisms to effectively manage challenges. By engaging in problem-solving approaches, seeking social support, and being mindful of avoidance behaviors, individuals can develop resilience and adaptive coping strategies to navigate life's difficulties successfully. The mean pre-board score for the entire sample is 74.10, with a standard deviation of 10.85. This provides an average measure of performance across all respondents, indicating the overall level of achievement in the pre-board examinations. The analysis revealed that none of the correlations between the challenges faced by LET takers and their pre-board performance are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Specifically, the correlation coefficients for personal, financial, parental, and total challenges are all negative, indicating a tendency for higher levels of challenges to be associated with lower pre-board performance, but these associations are not significant based on the p-values.

Keywords: *challenges, coping mechanisms, pre-board performance, descriptive correlational design*

Introduction

Taking a board Examination is a challenge to every degree holder. This is one of the pre-requisites for them to get a license in order to perform their chosen profession. For the aspiring teachers, they need to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers in order for them to get the license they need in practicing their profession. For the past years, the passing rate of the Licensure Examination for Teachers is neither bad nor good, yet, being known as the noblest profession, we see them as competitive and intelligent ones. The performance they showed in Licensure Examination should attest that they really are good and they will become an effective teacher for the learners. According to Fiscal and Roman (2022), for the past 10 years, LET results released by PRC showed that national passing rates of teacher education graduates are below 50%. Clearly, a gap exists in terms of competencies of teacher education graduates in the country. In response to this scenario, HEIs in the Philippines initiated variety of strategies to improve the Licensure results.

However, succeeding and having good performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers is not easy. Some would successfully make it to pass but some would unfortunately not make it. This is because there are lots of challenges that LET takers encountered during their preparation for the exam. These challenges may affect their performance in the actual exam. Although they are facing different challenges, there are some adjustments they do which is called a coping mechanism for them to deal with those challenges. Teachers are the one who molded the youngsters and every LET takers must perform well in the Licensure Examination for their performance to the board Examination would attest their performance as they perform their profession. If teachers are competitive the learners will be competitive too. If teachers are incompetent and ineffective, learners will not be able to get and learn the best from their teachers.

Challenge, sometimes perceived as stress, may be beneficial or detrimental to learning but the circumstances when it may be beneficial are not clear (Rudland, 2021). Coping could be described as humans' cognitive and/or behavioral efforts that are used to cope with external and internal demands under a stressful circumstance. There are different types of coping strategies. Emotion- focused coping is reactive and refers to attempting to regulate feelings and emotional responses to the stressor (e.g., anger, fear, sadness, anxiety, pressure). Problem-focused coping is proactive and refers to acting on the stressor, the environment, or oneself to address the problem in an attempt to decrease or eliminate the stress. It was reported that it is more effective to use problem-focused coping in controllable stressful circumstances, but it is more effective to use emotion-focused coping in uncontrollable stressful circumstances. A third type of coping, avoidance-focused coping, refers to cognitions and behaviors aimed at avoiding the stressful situation and reactions to it, such as distraction and diversion, and tends to be an initial reaction to stress (Ding et al., 2021).

A coping mechanism is a method of dealing with unhappiness, stress, or other potential issues. It is whatever a person does to handle negative emotions or problems. Coping mechanisms are compulsions, or habits formed over time, that serve to help a person manage with particular situations or stress levels (American Addiction Center 2023). Coping mechanism any conscious or nonconscious adjustment or adaptation that decreases tension and anxiety in a stressful experience or situation. Modifying maladaptive coping

mechanisms is often the focus of psychological interventions (APA, 2022).

The Republic Act (RA) 7836 known as the Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994 supported this study. The Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) strengthened the supervision and regulation of the teaching profession. The PRC then prescribed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Additionally, Article IV, Section 27 of the same Act stipulates the teachers' appointment to a teaching position in the government is to obtain a valid certificate of registration and a valid professional license from the Commission (Binayao, 2020).

Thus, the objective of this study is to determine what are those challenges and coping mechanisms that affects the pre-board performance of the LET takers. The challenges, coping mechanisms, and socio-demographic profile of LET takers was correlated to their pre-board performance. This study was conducted on the first quarter of 2024. The researcher is a licensed professional teacher and is credible to pursue this study because aside from being a teacher in profession, the researcher is a lecturer for LET review at Catalyst Pro Tutorial and Review Center where this study was conducted.

LET takers should really show good performance for they are expected to be the teachers of the future generations. It is essential to recognize the obstacles and coping strategies that impact one's performance in the LET pre-board examinations. By doing so, support can be provided to educators, aiding them in achieving exceptional results in the actual test. This assistance will demonstrate that educators are sufficiently competent to be esteemed and relied upon for the education of young individuals and all those pursuing knowledge.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between challenges and coping mechanisms of LET takers in Catalyst Pro Tutorial and Review Center to their pre-board performance. The study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents of the study in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. number of takes; and
 - 1.4. last school attended?
2. What are the challenges of let takers in terms of:
 - 2.1. personal
 - 2.2. parental; and
 - 2.3. financial?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of LET takers in terms of:
 - 3.1. problem-focused;
 - 3.2. social support; and
 - 3.3. avoidance?
4. What is the pre-board performance of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges of LET takers into their pre-board performance?
6. Is there a significant relationship between coping mechanisms of LET takers into their pre-board performance?
7. Is there a significant relationship between socio-demographic profile and pre-board performance?
8. Which level of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and socio-demographic profile significantly predict the pre-board performance of the respondents?
9. What action plan can be formulated based from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research used in describing socio-economic profile and the challenges and coping mechanisms of Let takers. It is also correlational research since the socio-economic profile, the challenges and, the coping mechanisms of let takers were correlated to the pre-board performance of the LET takers.

Respondents

The respondents of the study comprised reviewees currently enrolled in preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), with the intention of taking the examination scheduled for March 2024. These individuals were drawn from various private colleges and universities, reflecting a diverse pool of participants. Simple random sampling was employed to select respondents, ensuring that each potential participant had an equal chance of being included in the study. Although there were a total of 337 LET takers, only 130 of them actually participated in the study. These participants were divided into two rooms for the examination, with the respondents of the study situated in one room, while the remaining LET takers occupied the other room. The sample encompassed individuals from different state universities and colleges, contributing to the representation of a wide spectrum of educational backgrounds.

Furthermore, the demographics of the respondents revealed notable trends. A majority of the participants were female, which is consistent with the dominance of females in the teaching profession. Additionally, most respondents were first-time LET takers, indicative of their status as recent graduates entering the workforce. The age range of the respondents was predominantly concentrated between 21 to 24 years old, reflecting the youthful composition of the sample. These demographic characteristics provide valuable context for understanding the profile of the study participants and may have implications for their experiences, perspectives, and outcomes related to the licensure examination and the teaching profession.

Table 1. Respondents

<i>Description</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Number of actual respondents</i>
LET takers	337	130

Table 1 shows the respondents of the study. The respondents were the LET takers on March 17, 2024. The total number of respondents were 337 but the actual respondents were 130.

Instrument

The research instrument utilized in the study consisted of two main components: the coping strategy indicator developed by Dr. James H. Amirkhan from the Department of Psychology at California State University, Long Beach, and a questionnaire adapted from a previous study conducted by Herrero (2015). Specifically, the questionnaire was originally titled "An Examination of Factors Affecting the Passing Rates of the CPA Examination" and was further utilized in a study by Albina et al. (2021) entitled "Factors and Challenges Influencing the Criminologist Licensure Examination Performance through the Non-passers' Lens." This adapted questionnaire served as the instrument for assessing the challenges faced by LET (Licensure Examination for Teachers) takers.

The questionnaire underwent modifications by the researcher, who adjusted certain items to ensure their relevance and appropriateness for the study's respondents. This process of adaptation aimed to tailor the questionnaire to the specific context of LET takers, thereby enhancing its suitability for assessing their challenges effectively. Prior to full implementation, the questionnaire underwent pilot testing to evaluate its reliability and internal consistency. Pilot testing was conducted in a sponsored review class by MP Alimoden based in Marawi City.

The pilot test yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.791, indicating satisfactory internal consistency of the instrument. This value suggests that the items in the questionnaire are reliably measuring the intended constructs. Overall, the result of the pilot test provided evidence that the instrument demonstrates acceptable reliability and can effectively capture the challenges experienced by LET takers. Through careful adaptation and validation procedures, the research instrument was deemed suitable for use in the study, enabling the researchers to gather comprehensive data on the coping strategies and challenges faced by LET takers in preparation for the licensure examination.

Table 2. Reliability Analysis

<i>Study Variables</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>	<i>Description</i>
Coping Mechanism	.705	18	Acceptable
Challenges	.758	12	Acceptable
Overall Reliability	0.791	30	Acceptable

Table 2 presents Cronbach's alpha values for each study variable, which measure the internal consistency of the items within the variable. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher is generally considered acceptable for research purposes. The Cronbach's alpha values for the study variables are higher than the acceptable threshold of .7, indicating that the reliability of these variables is at least acceptable. This result suggests that the internal consistency of the items used to measure these study variables were met.

Thus, the instrument used in this study has overall acceptable internal consistency, indicating that it can be used for future research purposes.

Procedure

The process of gathering data for the study commenced following a pilot-testing phase conducted on December 15, 2023. Directly overseeing the study, the researcher played a hands-on role in facilitating the data collection process. Before initiating data collection, the researcher meticulously adhered to established protocols and procedures, ensuring that all necessary permissions were obtained to conduct the study. With a rigorous approach in place, the researcher proceeded to administer the questionnaire to the targeted respondents. Opting for a group administration method, the researcher provided the questionnaire to all participants simultaneously, fostering a cohesive and efficient data collection environment.

During this stage, participants were asked to answer the questionnaire collectively, implying a synchronous data collection process where responses were obtained concurrently from all participants. Once the respondents completed the questionnaire, the researcher promptly collected the answered questionnaires on the same day, maintaining a high level of timeliness and efficiency throughout the process. This swift turnaround in data collection minimized potential delays and ensured that the data remained fresh and reflective of the respondents' perspectives at that moment.

Following the completion of data collection, the gathered data were transferred to a statistician for comprehensive analysis. Afterwards, the researcher retrieved the result of the pre-board performance from the review center director. By collaborating with a statistician, the researcher sought to leverage expert insights and analytical techniques to derive meaningful interpretations from the collected data. This collaborative effort underscored the researcher's commitment to conducting robust statistical analyses, ultimately aiming to produce accurate and reliable findings. Through a meticulous approach encompassing pilot-testing, direct engagement with respondents, and collaboration with a statistician, the study's data gathering process strived to uphold the integrity, validity, and rigor of the research endeavor.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques was employed to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, Frequency and Percentage was used in analyzing the profile of the LET takers as to gender, age, status, and last attended schools.

For problem 2, 3, and 4 Frequency and Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation was used to determine the challenges and coping mechanisms, and pre-board performance of LET takers.

For problem 5, 6, and 7 Pearson Moment Correlation was used to determine the relationship between the socio-economic profile, the challenges and the coping mechanisms of LET takers into their LET performance.

For, problem 8 Multiple regression analysis was utilized to test if the predictors significantly affected the pre-board performance of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

The presentation and analysis of the information gathered from the respondents are the topics of this chapter. There are additional presentations of the findings' interpretations and implications.

Problem 1: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents of the study in terms of age, gender, number of takes, last school attended?

The distribution of the respondents' age, sex, number of takes, and last school attended is presented in the following sociodemographic profile.

Table 3. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
21-25	97	74.6
26-30	25	19.2
31-40	3	2.3
41-50	5	3.8
Total	130	100.0

Table 3 displays the age distribution of respondents surveyed, indicating the diversity of age groups within the sample. Almost all of the respondents, comprising 74.6%, fell within the age range of 21 to 25 years, reflecting a significant proportion of younger individuals. In contrast, a smaller but notable percentage, 19.2%, represented the 26 to 30 age group. The result further reveals a decreasing trend in participation with advancing age, as evidenced by only 2.3% falling within the 31 to 40 age bracket and 3.8% within the 41 to 50 range. This distribution suggests a skew towards younger individuals in the respondent pool.

Delos Angeles (2019) reported that the average age of graduates was 22.16 years, with a standard deviation of 3.12, indicating that they were older than the typical age for recent graduates of a four-year Teacher Education program when they took their licensing examination. Specifically, 40% were under 21 years old, 24.44% were exactly 21, and 35.56% were older than 21.

According to Lacanilao and Carpio's study from 2022, the majority of examinees who took the criminology board exams are in the age range of 20 and 25. This is because students who started college at the age of eighteen often graduate at the age of twenty-three.

Table 4. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	11	8.5
Female	119	91.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 4 displays the sex distribution among the respondents, highlighting a notable gender imbalance within the sample. The overwhelming majority, constituting 91.5% of the respondents, identified as female, while only 8.5% identified as male. In the article of Mark Anthony Llego (2019) it indicated that the majority of participants from 2010 to 2018 were female. Additionally, the research of Delos Angeles (2019) showed that a significant majority, 86.67%, of the LET candidates were female, and 91.11% were unmarried.

Soriano (2009) also found that the best predictors of LET success were the candidates' General Education GPA, USMICET GSA score, chosen course, and gender.

Table 5. Number of Takes of the Respondents

<i>Number of Takes</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
First Taker	98	75.4
Retaker	32	24.6
Total	130	100.0

Table 5 provides the frequency of takes among the respondents. Most of respondents, comprising 75.4%, identified themselves as first-takers, indicating a significant proportion of individuals encountering the subject matter for the first time. In contrast, a smaller percentage, 24.6%, identified as retakers, suggesting a cohort of respondents revisiting or engaging with the subject matter again. This distribution underscores the varying levels of familiarity or exposure among respondents, which could potentially influence their perspectives, responses, or behaviors.

The study of Fulgado (2020) revealed that First-time takers' performance at the College of Education Pililla Campus was consistent with being above passive levels. To measure educational programs' academic standards, the HEIs board test results are used both private and public. First-takers in their major was given the lowest rating in General Education and Professional Education, resulting in a low passage rate.

The license examination performance is also highly influenced by the examinee type (first taker or retaker), according to Cahapay and Toquero (2022) as stated by Pangngay (2023).

Table 6. Last School Attended of the Respondents

<i>Last School Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Public	82	63.1
Private	48	36.9
Total	130	100.0

Table 6 provides the last school attended by the respondents. The greater number of the respondents, comprising 63.1%, reported attending public schools, while 36.9% indicated attendance at private institutions. This distribution suggested a significant representation of individuals with diverse educational experiences, reflecting the accessibility of both private and public schooling within the surveyed population. The prevalence of respondents from public schools indicates a sizable portion of individuals who have been exposed to education provided by government-funded institutions. In contrast, the presence of respondents from private schools underscores the involvement of individuals who may have experienced education in privately funded or independent institutions.

Lagrador and Refozar (2020) noted that a significant number of tertiary-level students in the Philippines enroll in private (HEIs) due to the scarcity of space in state-run schools, a situation first noted by James in 1991. This trend has persisted into 2020, with the student population in private institutions continuing to rise, attributed to the national government's reduction in funding for State Universities and Colleges (SUCs).

Problem 2: What are the challenges of the respondents in terms of personal, parental, and financial?

The following shows the mean and standard deviation of the different indicators of personal, parental, and financial challenges of the respondents.

Table 7. Challenges of the Respondents in terms of Personal

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. The exam is very difficult to answer.	3.03	.60	<i>Agree</i>
2. The time allotted to finish the exam is not enough.	2.84	.73	<i>Agree</i>
3. Some items in the exam were not discussed in school.	2.80	.81	<i>Agree</i>
4. I was pressured by the personal and social consequences of failing the exam.	3.32	.73	<i>Agree</i>
5. The language used in the exam is difficult to understand.	2.47	.76	<i>Disagree</i>
6. I have no enough time to study or review.	2.26	.72	<i>Disagree</i>
Total Measure	2.79	.45	<i>Agree</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 7 contains the challenges reported by respondents with regard to personal indicators during examinations, along with their corresponding mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The mean score for each indicator provides an average score of respondents' agreement or disagreement with the statement, while the SD reflects the dispersion or variability of responses around the mean. Overall, the total mean score of 2.79 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding the challenges they face during examinations.

With a mean score of 3.32 and a modest level of variability ($SD = 0.73$), respondents indicated the highest level of agreement with the specific difficulty of feeling pressurized by the social and personal implications of failing the exam.

This highlights the significant impact of external pressures on respondents' examination experiences and emphasizes how critical it is to deal with pressures that affect academic achievement.

Additionally, respondents tended to agree that the exam difficulty, inadequate time allocation, and lack of coverage of exam topics in school were notable challenges, as indicated by mean scores ranging from 2.80 to 3.03 and corresponding SD values. These findings stress the necessity for educators to consider the appropriateness of exam content, ensure sufficient time for completion, and provide adequate preparation and support to mitigate perceived challenges.

Conversely, respondents disagreed with statements indicating difficulty understanding the language used in the examination and insufficient time for study or review, as reflected by mean scores of 2.47 and 2.26, respectively, and associated SD values. While these factors may not be perceived as significant challenges by most of the respondents, they still warrant attention to ensure equitable access and support for all students, particularly those facing language or time constraints. The aforementioned results emphasize the complex and varied obstacles that students encounter during exams, underscoring the significance of tackling both academic and non-academic pressures in order to foster student welfare and academic achievement.

According to Espartero (2022), there is a correlation between personal factors and the problems that arise in the CLE. This result validates Badua's (2020) findings, which confirms that there are students who perform exceptionally well academically but who fail the CLE because of personal issues.

Table 8. *Challenges of the Respondents in terms of Financial*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. It is very expensive to take the exam.	2.50	.79	Agree
2. I always have a shortage on my allowance	2.91	.77	Agree
3. I don't have a budget to purchase book reviewers and some other materials	2.82	.76	Agree
Total Measure	2.74	.62	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 8 presents the challenges reported by respondents in terms of financial indicators related to examinations, along with their corresponding mean scores and standard deviations (SD). Overall, the total mean score of 2.74 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding the financial challenges they face when preparing for examinations.

Among the specific financial challenges identified, respondents expressed the highest agreement with the statement that they always have a shortage on their allowance, with a mean score of 2.91 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.77$). This highlights the significant impact of financial constraints on respondents' ability to afford study materials, transportation, and other essential expenses related to examination preparation.

Additionally, respondents tended to agree that the cost of taking the examination as well as lack of a budget to purchase book reviewers and other materials were notable financial challenges, as indicated by mean scores of 2.50 and 2.82, respectively, and corresponding SD values. These results highlight the financial obstacles that students must overcome to acquire the materials required for efficient exam preparation, which can worsen inequality and impair academic achievement. These results highlight the necessity of removing financial obstacles in order to guarantee fair access to education and encourage student achievement.

According to Norazlan et al. (2023), the connection between financial difficulties and the academic results of Malaysian public university students can be effectively characterized by delayed financial aid, a scarcity of financial means, inadequate loans or scholarships, and poor financial planning. The research indicates that a number of students rely exclusively on educational loans or scholarships for funding. Others depend on their family's earnings, while some must find employment to support their education and daily living expenses. Financial difficulties can be brought on by insufficient funding, and this can then negatively affect students' academic performance.

Table 9. *Challenges of the Respondents in terms of Parental*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I have too many family responsibilities.	2.56	.79	Agree
2. I don't feel much support from my family	1.88	.77	Disagree
3. family problems disrupt my focus in reviewing	2.32	.96	Disagree
Total Measure	2.25	.61	Disagree

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 9 outlines the challenges reported by respondents in terms of parental indicators related to examination preparation. The total mean score of 2.25 suggests a general disagreement among respondents regarding the parental challenges they face when preparing for examinations.

Among the specific parental challenges identified, respondents disagreed most strongly with the statement that they don't feel much support from their family, with a mean score of 1.88 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.77$). This indicates that greater number of respondents perceive a supportive environment from their families, which can positively influence their motivation and ability to prepare for exams effectively.

Additionally, respondents tended to disagree that family problems disrupt their focus in reviewing, as indicated by a mean score of 2.32 and a corresponding SD value. While family responsibilities were acknowledged as somewhat burdensome, with a mean score of 2.56, respondents did not perceive them as significantly disruptive to their examination preparation.

Overall, these findings suggest that, while some respondents face family responsibilities, they generally perceive a supportive family environment that aids their examination preparation. This stresses how crucial familial support in facilitating academic success and underscores the need for interventions that strengthen family involvement and support networks for students. By fostering supportive family environments, educational stakeholders can enhance students' resilience and ability to navigate academic challenges effectively.

According to Lacanilao and Carpio (2022), the examinees' morale is raised and they are an inspiration to the family. He added that numerous studies have demonstrated the significant impact families have on their children's academic success. The significance of the examinees' family in terms of offering them both financial and emotional support has also been shown. It is indeed that when life gets tough, it is the family that we turned into for support.

Albina (2022) asserts that support from parents is also an essential element of exam preparation. More specifically, it works best when parents don't expect their kids to start working as soon as they graduate to ensure their financial support. One participant narrated that: "Parents should understand that preparation for the exam is needed. There are parents who expect their children to work or give back right after graduating. Lucky are those who have parents who understand."

Table 10. Consolidated Findings of the Challenges of the Respondents

Challenges	Mean	SD	Description
Personal	2.79	.45	Agree
Financial	2.74	.62	Agree
Parental	2.25	.61	Disagree
Total Measure	2.59	.43	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents the consolidated findings of the challenges reported by respondents across various domains, including personal, financial, and parental indicators. The overall mean score of 2.59 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding the challenges they face when preparing for examinations, encompassing personal and financial domains.

Specifically, respondents expressed the highest agreement with personal challenges, with a mean score of 2.79 and a low level of variability ($SD = 0.45$).

This indicates that respondents perceive personal factors, such as exam difficulty, time constraints, and pressure, as significant challenges impacting their examination preparation.

Financial challenges were also acknowledged by respondents, with a mean score of 2.74 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.62$). This highlights the financial barriers students face in accessing resources necessary for effective exam preparation, such as study materials and transportation, which can hinder academic performance and exacerbate inequalities.

In contrast, respondents tended to disagree with parental challenges, as indicated by a mean score of 2.25 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.61$). While some respondents reported family responsibilities, the majority perceived a supportive family environment that aids their examination preparation, underscoring the importance of familial support in facilitating academic success.

Therefore, these results highlight the intricate nature of the issues that students deal with when studying for exams, which include issues related to their personal, financial, and family lives.

Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions and support mechanisms that alleviate academic stressors, mitigate financial barriers, and strengthen family involvement and support networks. Educational stakeholders may establish a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that enables all students to achieve academically by acknowledging and addressing the variety of problems that students experience.

Al (2020) asserted that financial circumstances have a major influence on a student's academic performance, as noted by Norazlan. Financial difficulties are a severe problem that need attention since they can cause a variety of other challenges, including poor academic performance and health.

Additionally, Saeed et al. (2023) discovered that when kids experience familial support, they feel more respected and confident, which in turn helps them achieve academically. There was a statistically significant relationship between academic achievement and friends and family.

Problem 3: What are the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of problem solving, social support, and avoidance?

The mean and standard deviation of the respondents' coping techniques for problem-solving, seeking social support, and avoidance are shown below.

Table 11. *Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents in terms of Problem Solving*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Brainstormed all possible solutions before deciding what to do	3.51	.55	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
2. Formed a plan of action in your mind	3.44	.62	<i>Agree</i>
3. Set some goals for yourself to deal with the situation	3.60	.49	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
4. Tried to solve the problems	3.39	.58	<i>Agree</i>
5. Thought about what needed to be done to straight things out	3.28	.55	<i>Agree</i>
6. Turned your full attention to solving the problem	3.31	.61	<i>Agree</i>
Total Measure	3.42	.36	<i>Agree</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49 – *Strongly Disagree* 1.50-2.49 – *Disagree* 2.50-3.49 – *Agree* 3.50-4.00 – *Strongly Agree*

Table 11 presents the coping mechanisms employed by respondents in terms of problem-solving strategies. An overall mean score of 3.42 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of problem-solving strategies in coping with challenges.

Among the specific problem-solving indicators, respondents strongly agreed with the statements related to proactive problem-solving approaches, such as brainstorming all possible solutions, forming an action plan, and setting goals to deal with the situation. These coping mechanisms received high mean scores ranging from 3.44 to 3.60, indicating a consensus among respondents regarding their effectiveness in addressing challenges. It demonstrates that the respondents understand the value of goal-setting and proactive planning for efficient problem-solving and management.

Additionally, respondents agreed with statements related to taking action to solve problems, thinking about necessary steps to address the situation, and dedicating full attention to problem-solving efforts. While these coping mechanisms received slightly lower mean scores compared to proactive strategies, they still indicate a general consensus among respondents regarding their efficacy in managing challenges.

These results emphasize the significance of employing proactive problem-solving strategies in coping with challenges effectively. By engaging in proactive planning, goal-setting, and action-taking, individuals can enhance their ability to address and overcome obstacles they encounter. Educators, counselors, and other support personnel can use these insights to promote the growth of students' efficient problem-solving abilities, thereby empowering them to navigate academic and personal challenges more successfully.

According to Cornejo (2020), coping skills can help individuals navigate through challenges brought on when experiencing stress, and would help students to be self-reliant, solve problems, and make informed choices which in turn promote their physical and psychological well-being.

Table 12. *Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents in terms of Social Support*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Let your feelings out to a friend	2.89	.63	<i>Agree</i>
2. Accepted sympathy and understanding from someone	3.32	.61	<i>Agree</i>
3. Talked to people about the situation because talking about it helped you to feel better	3.15	.74	<i>Agree</i>
4. Confided your fears and worries to a friend	2.85	.66	<i>Agree</i>
5. Told people about the situation because just talking about it helped you to come up with solutions	2.97	.68	<i>Agree</i>
6. Accepted sympathy and understanding from friends who had the same problem	3.08	.68	<i>Agree</i>
Total Measure	3.04	.41	<i>Agree</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49 – *Strongly Disagree* 1.50-2.49 – *Disagree* 2.50-3.49 – *Agree* 3.50-4.00 – *Strongly Agree*

Table 12 outlines the coping mechanisms utilized by respondents in terms of seeking social support. An overall mean score of 3.04 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of seeking social support as a coping mechanism.

Among the specific social support indicators, respondents agreed with various forms of seeking encouragement from friends and acquaintances. They expressed agreement with letting their feelings out to a friend, accepting sympathy and understanding from someone, talking to people about the situation for emotional relief, confiding their fears and worries to a friend, and accepting sympathy and understanding from friends who had experienced similar problems. These coping mechanisms received mean scores ranging from 2.85 to 3.32, indicating a consensus among respondents regarding their efficacy in seeking social support to cope with challenges.

Overall, these findings highlight the importance of seeking social support as a coping strategy for successfully handling challenges. By reaching out to friends and acquaintances for emotional support, understanding, and shared experiences, individuals can alleviate distress, gain perspective, and access resources to navigate challenges more successfully. Teachers, counselors, and other support staff members can use these insights to highlight the value of social support networks and motivate students to ask for help from peers and reliable people when they are having problems. This creates an atmosphere of support, which strengthens people's resilience and capacity to handle life's obstacles.

Mclean et al. (2022) social support is crucial for students' wellbeing and academic success. According to Briones and Romero's (2020) research, peer validation and support play a vital role in enhancing their self-assurance. The fact that they are able to accept complete responsibility for their conduct also shows that they have reached adulthood. "I am willing to improve myself for my own betterment and am open to criticism," which comes next, with an extraordinarily high weighted mean of 4.6 (rank 3). This parameter shows that students are open to correction for their self-improvement.

In line with Cornejo's (2020) findings, students who perceive higher levels of peer social support are inclined to exhibit higher levels of self-esteem and superior academic performance.

Table 13. *Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents in terms of Avoidance*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Watched television more than usual	2.27	.88	<i>Disagree</i>
2. Tried to distract yourself from the problem	2.65	.94	<i>Agree</i>
3. Slept more than usual	2.51	.82	<i>Agree</i>
4. Avoided being with people in general	2.50	.78	<i>Agree</i>
5. Buried yourself in a hobby or sports activity to avoid the problem	2.71	.84	<i>Agree</i>
6. Tried to carefully plan a course of action rather than acting on impulse	3.02	.65	<i>Agree</i>
Total Measure	2.61	.51	<i>Agree</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 13 presents the coping mechanisms employed by respondents in terms of avoidance strategies. The respondents' overall mean score of 2.61 indicates that they generally agree that avoidance coping methods are used.

Among the specific avoidance indicators, respondents tended to agree with various strategies aimed at avoiding or distracting themselves from the problem. They concurred that the best strategies for addressing a problem was to try to divert their attention from it, sleep more than normal, avoid social situations in general, and immerse oneself in pastimes or extracurricular activities. These coping mechanisms received mean scores ranging from 2.27 to 2.71, indicating a consensus among respondents regarding their inclination to use avoidance strategies when facing challenges.

However, respondents disagreed with the statement about watching television more than usual as a coping mechanism, as indicated by a mean score of 2.27 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.88$). This suggests that while respondents may engage in certain avoidance behaviors, such as distraction or isolation, they may not necessarily resort to excessive television consumption as a coping technique.

These findings highlight the prevalence of avoidance coping strategies among respondents when faced with challenges. While avoidance habits could offer momentary respite from stress or discomfort, they might not address the underlying problems and might eventually make it more challenging to successfully cope and solve challenges. Educators, counselors, and other support personnel can use these insights to promote the development of healthier coping strategies that encourage active problem-solving and resilience in managing challenges effectively.

As He (2023) pointed out, avoidance coping might occasionally be advantageous in the near run. Long-term use, however, may result in elevated stress, intensified negative emotions, and diminished academic performance. Furthermore, investigations suggest that cognitive avoidance may have a negative impact on academic performance. Research indicates that students who choose not to seek help for their psychological or emotional issues are more inclined to react negatively to stress.

Table 14. *Consolidated Findings of the Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Problem- Solving	3.42	.36	<i>Agree</i>
Social Support	3.04	.41	<i>Agree</i>
Avoidance	2.61	.51	<i>Agree</i>
Total Measure	3.03	.29	<i>Agree</i>

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49 – Disagree 2.50-3.49 – Agree 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

Table 14 presents the consolidated findings of the coping mechanisms employed by respondents across various domains, including problem-solving, social support, and avoidance strategies. The respondents appear to be generally in agreement with the usefulness of coping methods in handling obstacles, as indicated by the overall mean score of 3.03.

Specifically, respondents expressed the highest level of agreement with problem-solving strategies, with a mean score of 3.42 and a low level of variability ($SD = 0.36$). This indicates that respondents perceive proactive problem-solving approaches, such as brainstorming solutions, forming plans of action, and setting goals, as effective strategies for coping with challenges.

Respondents also agreed with seeking social support as a coping mechanism, with a mean score of 3.04 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.41$). This suggests that the participants acknowledge the significance of obtaining emotional assistance, comprehension, and mutual experiences from friends and acquaintances in order to proficiently handle obstacles.

Additionally, respondents tended to agree with avoidance adaptive techniques, like distraction, isolation, and engaging in activities to avoid the problem, as indicated by a mean score of 2.61 and a moderate level of variability ($SD = 0.51$). Avoidance techniques may reduce stress momentarily, but they may not deal with underlying problems and may eventually make it more difficult to solve problems and cope well.

All things considered, these results highlight how crucial it is to use a variety of coping strategies in order to handle obstacles successfully. Through problem-solving techniques, social support, and awareness of avoidance patterns, people can cultivate adaptable coping mechanisms and resilience to effectively manage life's challenges. These insights can be used by educators, counselors, and other support staff to help students develop healthy coping mechanisms and to create a supportive atmosphere that improves people's capacity to deal with difficulties.

According to Del Rosario (2023), Seeking social support from friends, family or support groups can be a helpful way to vent emotions and receive advice. Furthermore, his research showed no connection at all between respondents' coping and stress management techniques and their academic achievement.

Problem 4: What is the pre-board performance of the respondents?

The table below shows the distribution of frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of the respondents' pre-board score.

Table 15 presents the pre-board performance of the respondents, categorized by pre-board score ranges. The pre-board score ranges include 90-100, 85-89, 80-84, 75-79, and below 74, each representing different levels of performance.

Table 15. *Pre-Board Performance of the Respondents*

First taker	Retaker	Pre-Board Percentile Score	Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
0	1	90-100	Outstanding	1	0.8	74.10 (10.85)
12	3	85-89	Very Satisfactory	15	11.5	
30	5	80-84	Satisfactory	35	26.9	
20	9	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	29	22.3	
36	14	Below-74	Less Satisfactory	50	38.5	
Total				130	100.0	

Several of the respondents scored below 74, with 38.5% falling into this category. This implies that a sizable percentage of participants had less than optimal pre-board scores. Additionally, 26.9% of respondents scored within the 80-84 range, indicating a satisfactory performance level. Meanwhile, 22.3% achieved fairly satisfactory scores falling within the 75-79 range. Relatively fewer respondents scored within the 85-89 range, with 11.5% achieving a very satisfactory performance level. Only one respondent, representing 0.8% of the sample, attained an outstanding pre-board score falling within the 90-100 range.

The mean pre-board score for the entire sample is 74.10, with a standard deviation of 10.85. This provides an average measure of performance across all respondents, indicating the overall level of achievement in the pre-board examinations.

These results offer insightful information into the distribution of pre-board performance among respondents, highlighting the varying levels of achievement and proficiency. Understanding the pre-board performance of respondents can inform educators and policymakers about the academic preparedness and potential support needs of students. It can also guide interventions aimed at improving academic performance and promoting student success.

According the findings of Fiscal and Roman (2022), pre-board examinations can validly predict performance in the LET. Similarly, the pre-board exam designed by the college of education faculty is a reliable indicator of performance on the LET. Furthermore, the institution meets the needs of the students in terms of offering competencies, particularly in the field of general education. The institution may, however, concentrate on offering reviews to the graduates particularly in the areas of professional education and major field of concentration in order to give attention to other areas. This is attainable through offering LET applicants an intensive curriculum that includes ongoing monitoring and assessment. Since the students' pre-LET performance is a reliable indicator of their real LET performance, religious implementation through a rigorous monitoring approach is possible.

Table 16 presents the pre-board performance of the respondents, categorized by pre-board score ranges. The pre-board score ranges include 90- 100, 85-89, 80-84, 75-79, and below 74, each representing different levels of performance.

Table 16. *Pre-Board General Education Performance of the Respondents*

Pre-Board Percentile Score	General Education Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
90-100	Outstanding	1	0.8	74.54 (11.25)
85-89	Very Satisfactory	23	17.7	
80-84	Satisfactory	29	22.3	20.8
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	27	20.8	
Below-74	Less Satisfactory	50	38.5	
Total		130	100.0	

Upon analyzing the respondents' pre-board general education performance, valuable insights were obtained. Among the respondents, a significant proportion, comprising 38.5%, scored below 74, indicating a less satisfactory performance level. Moreover, 20.8% achieved scores falling within the 75-79 range, while 22.3% attained satisfactory scores within the 80-84 range. Additionally, 17.7% of respondents achieved a very satisfactory performance level, scoring between 85-89. Remarkably, only one respondent, representing 0.8% of the sample, attained an outstanding score falling within the 90-100 range. The mean pre-board percentile score for the entire sample is 74.54, with a standard deviation of 11.25, reflecting the overall performance level.

These findings suggest a varying degree of performance among the respondents, with a notable proportion falling below satisfactory levels. It underscores the importance of identifying and addressing the factors contributing to lower performance levels, such as inadequate preparation or comprehension gaps in general education topics. Educational institutions and review centers can utilize these findings to tailor their instructional approaches and support mechanisms to better meet the needs of LET takers and improve their overall academic performance in the licensure examination.

Table 17. *Pre-Board Professional Education Performance of the Respondents*

Pre-Board Percentile Score	Professional Education Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
90-100	Outstanding	1	0.8	73.74 (10.84)
85-89	Very Satisfactory	12	9.2	
80-84	Satisfactory	39	30.0	18.5
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	24	18.5	
Below-74	Less Satisfactory	54	41.5	
Total		130	100.0	

The examination of the pre-board professional education performance of the respondents reveals notable insights into their academic achievements. Among the respondents, a significant proportion, comprising 41.5%, scored below 74, indicating a less satisfactory performance level. Moreover, 18.5% attained scores within the 75-79 range, while 30.0% achieved satisfactory scores within the 80-84 range. Additionally, 9.2% of respondents achieved a very satisfactory performance level, scoring between 85-89. Remarkably, only one respondent, representing 0.8% of the sample, attained an outstanding score falling within the 90-100 range. The mean pre-board percentile score for the entire sample is 73.74, with a standard deviation of 10.84, reflecting the overall performance level.

These findings underscore the varying degrees of performance among the respondents, with a notable proportion falling below satisfactory levels. It highlights the necessity of identifying and addressing the factors contributing to lower performance levels, such as the adequacy of instructional resources or gaps in understanding professional education concepts.

Educational institutions and review centers can utilize these findings to refine their educational strategies and provide targeted support to enhance the professional education proficiency of LET takers and improve their overall academic performance in the licensure examination.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the challenges of LET takers into their pre-board performance?

The following shows the r-value and p-value of the respondents' pre-board performance based on Pearson correlation.

Table 18 shows the association, as indicated by Pearson correlation coefficients (r-values) and corresponding p-values, between the difficulties faced by LET takers and their pre-board performance.

According to the data, there is no statistically significant link, at the 0.05 level, between the difficulties faced by LET takers and their pre-board performance. In particular, there is a propensity for larger levels of challenges to be related with lower pre-board performance,

as indicated by the negative correlation coefficients for personal, financial, parental, and total challenges; nevertheless, the p-values do not support the significance of these correlations.

Table 18. *Relationship between the Challenges of LET Takers and their Pre-Board Performance*

Challenges of LET Takers	Pre-Board Performance		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Personal	-.114	.195	Not significant
Financial	-.058	.515	Not significant
Parental	-.094	.290	Not significant
Total Measure	-.112	.204	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation not significant at .05 level

These results suggested that, based on the sample analyzed, there is no clear linear relationship between the challenges faced by LET takers and their pre-board performance. While it might be intuitive to expect that facing more challenges would negatively impact academic performance, the lack of significant correlations in this study indicates that other factors not captured in this analysis may play a more influential role in determining pre-board performance.

The results of this study have implications for future research into the intricate relationship between the difficulties encountered by LET participants and their academic achievement. When creating interventions targeted at enhancing pre-board performance and assisting LET takers, educators and legislators must take a wider range of variables into account, including study habits, test-taking abilities, and access to educational resources.

Additionally, tailored support mechanisms should be developed to address the specific challenges faced by LET takers, including personalized academic counseling, financial assistance programs, and family support initiatives.

According to Espartero (2022), all of the criteria that respondents said had a significant impact on their success on the criminologist licensing examination were: the student factor, the home and family aspect, the school factor, the review center factor, and the personal component. Moreover, the participants hold comparable perspectives concerning the elements influencing the licensing exam.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the coping mechanisms of the respondents into their pre-board performance?

The following shows relationship between the Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents and their Pre-Board Performance using Pearson's r correlation.

Table 19. *Relationship between the Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents and their Pre- Board Performance*

Coping Mechanisms	Pre-Board Performance		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Problem- Solving	.049	.577	Not significant
Social Support	.029	.740	Not significant
Avoidance	.117	.186	Not significant
Total Measure	.104	.237	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation not significant at .05 level

Table 19 presents the relationship between the coping mechanisms utilized by respondents and their pre-board performance, as determined by Pearson correlation coefficients (r-values) and corresponding p-values.

The analysis indicated that none of the correlations between the coping mechanisms utilized by respondents and their pre-board performance are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Specifically, the correlation coefficients for problem-solving, social support, avoidance, and the total measure are all close to zero and have high p-values, indicating that there is no clear linear relationship between these coping mechanisms and pre-board performance based on the sample analyzed.

These results suggested that, while coping mechanisms may play a role in how individuals manage challenges, they may not directly influence academic performance on pre-board examinations.

Educators and support personnel should continue to encourage the development of healthy coping strategies among students, as these can positively impact overall well-being and resilience, even if they do not directly influence academic performance on pre-board examinations. Additionally, interventions aimed at improving pre-board performance should consider a holistic approach that addresses a range of factors, including academic skills, social support networks, and stress management techniques.

Overall, while coping mechanisms may not directly predict pre-board performance, they remain valuable tools for individuals to navigate challenges and enhance their overall academic experience.

According to Del Rosario (2023) college students have been shown to experience significant stress due to their academic load, especially the major of their course. When it comes to stress paying attention to the student's stress coping strategies is necessary. Also,

academic performance is influenced partly by their interpretation and adaptation to stressful conditions.

Problem 7: Is there a significant relationship between the socio- demographic profile and pre-board performance of the respondents?

The table below shows the relationship between the Socio-Demographic Profile and Pre-Board Performance of the Respondents based on Point-biserial correlation.

Table 20. Relationship between the Socio-Demographic Profile and Pre-Board Performance of the Respondents

Socio-Demographic Profiles	Pre-Board Performance		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Age=21-25	.032	.718	Not significant
Gender=Male	-.202*	.021	Significant
Number of Takes=First Taker	.062	.481	Not significant
Last School Attended=Private	-.151	.086	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Point-Biserial Correlation *significant at .05 level not significant at .05 level Reference category: 26+ years for age, female for gender, retaker for number of takes, and public for last school attended

Table 20 presents the relationship between the socio-demographic profiles of the respondents and their pre-board performance, as determined by Point- Biserial correlation coefficients (r-values) and corresponding p-values. The analysis revealed that the correlation between gender and pre-board performance is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, with a moderate negative correlation coefficient of -0.202. This suggests that being male is associated with lower pre-board performance compared to being female.

On the other hand, the correlations between age group, number of takes, and last school attended with pre-board performance are not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This indicates that there is no clear linear relationship between these socio-demographic factors and pre-board performance based on the sample analyzed.

These results highlight the importance of considering gender differences when examining pre-board performance among respondents. Educators and policymakers should explore potential factors contributing to the observed gender disparity in pre-board performance and develop targeted interventions to support male students in improving their academic achievement.

While age group, number of takes, and last school attended did not show significant correlations with pre-board performance in this analysis, it is essential to recognize that socio-demographic factors can interact with other variables to influence. Blaze (2019) revealed that gender was found to have a significant effect on academic performance, and exerted suppression effects on the results. Furthermore, females have been found to have better ability to retrieve information from their long-term memory over males.

Problem 8: Which level of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and socio- demographic profile significantly predict the preboard performance of the respondents?

The table below shows the result of multiple regression analysis that predict the preboard performance of the respondents.

Table 21 presents the results of a multiple regression analysis aiming to predict pre-board performance based on various predictors, including challenges, coping mechanisms, and socio-demographic profiles.

Table 21. Multiple Regression Analysis Results of Predicting the Pre-Board Performance by the Challenges, Coping Mechanisms and Socio-Demographic Profiles

Predictors	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	P-value	Remarks
(Constant)	87.531	13.550	6.460	.000	Significant
Personal	-2.679	2.459	-1.090	.278	Not significant
Financial	.039	1.813	.022	.983	Not significant
Parental	-.919	1.721	-.534	.594	Not significant
Problem Solving	-1.498	2.881	-.520	.604	Not significant
Social Support	-.519	2.372	-.219	.827	Not significant
Avoidance	2.251	1.925	1.169	.245	Not significant
Age=21-25	-.693	2.602	-.266	.791	Not significant
Sex=Male	-8.247	3.532	-2.335*	.021	Significant
Number of Takes=First Taker	.658	2.741	.240	.811	Not significant
Last School Attended=Private	-3.890	2.096	-1.856	.066	Not significant

Note: *significant at .05 level Reference category: 26+ years for age, female for gender, retaker for number of takes, and public for last school attended

The analysis reveals that the constant term is statistically significant (p < 0.05), indicating that there is a significant intercept when all other predictors are held constant.

Among the predictors, only gender shows a statistically significant effect on pre-board performance ($p = 0.021$). Being male is associated with a decrease in pre-board performance, with an estimated coefficient (B) of -8.247 . This suggests that male respondents tend to have lower pre-board performance compared to female respondents, all other factors being equal.

However, none of the other predictors—personal challenges, financial challenges, parental challenges, problem-solving strategies, social support, avoidance behaviors, age group, number of takes, and last school attended— show statistically significant effects on pre-board performance (all p -values >0.05). This indicates that, in this analysis, these factors do not have a significant independent influence on pre-board performance when other predictors are taken into account.

While several predictors may not independently demonstrate statistically significant effects on pre-board performance, it is crucial to remember that they may nevertheless have practical value or combine with other variables to affect academic outcomes. As a whole, the findings indicate that pre-board performance is significantly influenced by gender, with male respondents typically performing worse than female respondents.

Asante et al. (2023) stated that in the tertiary level, female students had a slightly higher mean rank of CGPA than male students, although the difference was not statistically significant. A statistically significant difference was found in the subjective evaluation of academic performance, as indicated by a chi-square test, with most female participants indicating better performance than their male counterparts. At this level, it appeared that female students benefited more from the exploratory teaching strategy. Additionally, parental motivation and support, along with campaigns for women's empowerment, positively influenced female students. Although female students had a higher likelihood of dedicating their time to studying, male students engaged more in extracurricular activities and economic pursuits. These male activities are thought to be influenced by broader socioeconomic and cultural factors.

According to Albina et al. (2021), the success of the Criminologist Licensure Examination is highly influenced by the home and family factors, but the factors related to students, schools, review centers, and personal factors have average effects. Moreover, some exam subjects were not covered in class, the exam is extremely difficult to answer, and the respondents felt stressed by the social and personal repercussions of failing. These are only a few of the difficulties involved in preparing for and taking the CLE. Ten topics that emerged as determinants influencing CLE success were revealed by the qualitative data. Among these include a fascination with an emphasis on B.S. Criminology, parent's moral and monetary assistance, availability of classrooms, laboratory equipment, and physical facilities, and availability of skilled and motivated staff personnel. Furthermore, nine theme clusters surfaced as obstacles related to getting ready for and taking the CLE. These include not being well-prepared for the exam due to work obligations, feeling under pressure to perform well on the test due to social and personal repercussions, being unfamiliar with exam vocabulary, and taking an extremely challenging exam.

Conclusions

This study concluded that respondents commonly face challenges in exam preparation, particularly in personal and financial domains, while also highlighting the importance of familial support. Proactive coping mechanisms, notably problem-solving strategies, were valued among respondents. However, pre-board performance varied, with a notable proportion scoring below satisfactory levels. Addressing these challenges and promoting effective coping strategies are crucial for enhancing academic achievement and supporting student success.

Thus, this study concluded that while challenges and coping mechanisms showed no significant correlation with pre-board performance, gender emerged as a significant factor, with male respondents exhibiting lower scores. Despite other socio-demographic factors not showing significant correlations, the findings underscore the importance of addressing gender disparities in academic achievement. However, the complex nature of pre-board performance suggests that additional unexamined factors may play a role in influencing outcomes.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made to various stakeholders.

For review centers and teacher education institutions, it is imperative to recognize and address the prevalent challenges faced by LET takers, especially in personal and financial domains. These institutions can enhance their support mechanisms by offering tailored resources and guidance to assist students in managing these obstacles effectively. Moreover, integrating comprehensive training programs within the curriculum that emphasize problem-solving skills and social support networks can better equip future educators for the rigors of licensure exams.

LET takers themselves can benefit from adopting proactive coping strategies, such as seeking social support and utilizing problem-solving techniques, to navigate challenges more effectively during exam preparation.

Parents play a crucial role in providing emotional and academic support to their children. Thus, fostering a supportive home environment that encourages open communication and offers resources for exam preparation can positively impact student performance.

Lastly, for future researchers, further exploration into the nuanced factors influencing pre-board performance beyond those examined in this study is recommended. This could involve investigating additional socio-demographic factors, as well as exploring the role of

individual differences and external influences on exam readiness and academic achievement.

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